

Linguistic Belonging among Non-Native English-Speaking Faculty in Internationalized Higher Education: Evidence from the UAE

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Abstract: This study examines linguistic belonging as a dimension of professional experience among non-native English-speaking faculty in English-medium instruction (EMI) higher education in the United Arab Emirates. While EMI research has focused largely on language proficiency and native-speaker ideologies, less attention has been paid to how language shapes everyday participation, recognition, and professional voice in academic workplaces. Drawing on a cross-sectional survey of 245 faculty members across public and private universities, the study explores how linguistic belonging relates to institutional climate, individual linguistic resources, and disciplinary context. Linguistic belonging is measured using a seven-item index that captures self-reported linguistic disconnection in English-mediated interactions. Ordinary least squares regression shows that greater workplace inclusion and higher self-rated English proficiency are associated with lower linguistic disconnection. In contrast, demographic characteristics, academic rank, institutional type, teaching experience, and prior residence in English-speaking countries are not significant predictors. Disciplinary differences are also observed, underscoring contextual variation.

Anahtar Sözcükler:

Dilsel aidiyet
Eğitim Dili İngilizce Olan Öğretim
Ana dili İngilizce olmayan öğretim üyeleri
İş yaşamında kapsayıcılık
Çok dillilik

Uluslararası Yükseköğretimde Ana Dili İngilizce Olmayan Akademisyenlerin Dilsel Aidiyet Deneyimleri: BAE Verileriyle Bir Analiz

Özet
Bu çalışma, Birleşik Arap Emirlikleri'ndeki İngilizce eğitim veren (EMI) yükseköğretim kurumlarında çalışan, ana dili İngilizce olmayan öğretim üyelerinin mesleki deneyimlerinin bir boyutu olarak "dilsel aidiyet" konusunu incelemektedir. EMI araştırmaları bugüne kadar büyük ölçüde dil yeterliliği ve yerel konuşmacı ideolojilerine odaklanmış olsa da dilin akademik çalışma ortamlarındaki günlük katılımı, tanınmayı ve mesleki ifade gücünü nasıl şekillendirdiği üzerinde daha az durulmuştur. Kamu ve vakıf üniversitelerinde görev yapan 245 öğretim üyesiyle gerçekleştirilen kesitsel bir ankete dayanan çalışma; dilsel aidiyetin kurum iklimi, bireysel dilsel kaynaklar ve disiplinler arası bağlamla olan ilişkisini araştırmaktadır. Dilsel aidiyet, İngilizce aracılığıyla kurulan etkileşimlerdeki "dilsel kopukluk" hissini ölçen yedi maddelik bir indeks üzerinden değerlendirilmiştir. En küçük kareler regresyon (OLS) analizi sonuçları, daha yüksek iş yeri kapsayıcılığı ve yüksek öz-değerlendirmeli İngilizce yeterliliğinin, düşük dilsel kopukluk düzeyiyle ilişkili olduğunu göstermektedir. Buna karşın; demografik özellikler, akademik unvan, kurum türü, öğretmenlik deneyimi ve daha önce İngilizce konuşulan ülkelerde ikamet etmiş olma durumu anlamlı birer yordayıcı değildir. Ayrıca, disiplinler arası farklılıklar da gözlemlenmiş olup bu durum bağlamsal değişkenliğin önemini vurgulamaktadır.

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1. Introduction

In contemporary higher education, English operates as more than simply a medium of instruction; it functions as a central mechanism through which academic work is circulated, evaluated, and legitimized globally. Driven by globalization, institutions in non-Anglophone settings have substantially expanded English-medium instruction (EMI), triggering a surge in transnational academic mobility (Altbach & Knight, 2007; Macaro *et al.*, 2018). Scholars increasingly migrate to systems where English is the professional lingua franca, even if it remains foreign to the wider society. However, as Liddicoat (2016) argues, institutional policies often treat language merely as a technical instrument, ignoring its central role in shaping academic life. This oversight frequently obscures the linguistic and relational complexities that accompany English-dominant work, particularly for scholars whose primary language is not English—complexities that manifest not merely as communication challenges, but as fundamental struggles over professional voice and epistemic authority.

These dynamics are particularly salient in the United Arab Emirates (UAE). Over the last two decades, the UAE has rapidly diversified its higher education sector by adopting EMI and relying heavily on an international workforce to staff public and private universities, including international branch campuses. While faculty are recruited based on demonstrated professional competence, their technical proficiency does not necessarily ensure social integration. Instead, the context creates complex conditions of recognition. For Emirati and Arabic-speaking scholars, professional legitimacy is often contingent on performing expertise in a foreign language (English), despite Arabic being the dominant societal language (AlKhatib *et al.*, 2021). Conversely, for non-Arabic-speaking expatriates, the expectation to communicate predominantly in English can act as a mechanism of social exclusion, isolating them from the informal Arabic-mediated interactions that often underpin institutional bonding. Thus, despite high levels of linguistic competence, the feeling of belonging remains precarious, contingent on how institutional culture bridges these linguistic divides.

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To navigate these layered conditions, this study views linguistic belonging from a post-structuralist perspective: not as a fixed attribute, but as a relational practice negotiated within historically and institutionally structured power relations (Norton, 2013). Seen through this lens, one's sense of belonging is not static; just as an academic identity evolves as a scholar progresses through different career ranks and institutional contexts, linguistic belonging fluctuates depending on contextual and situational variables. In the EMI context of UAE universities, English is empowered beyond its peripheral role in wider society, as academic recognition and professional legitimacy depend heavily on the mastery of English for academic purposes.

Furthermore, universities with multicultural faculty function as a Community of Practice (Wenger, 1998), where membership is enacted through mutual engagement; yet, in English-dominant settings, this engagement is closely entwined with linguistic performance. Non-native English-speaking (NNES) academics consequently navigate tensions between the linguistic resources of their first language (L1) and the professional demands of their additional language (L2). These tensions often result in a hybrid professional existence—akin to Whitchurch’s (2013) “Third Space”—which, in the context of this study, is re-conceptualized as a contested boundary within a Community of Practice. Unlike studies in Anglophone settings that focus on linguistic deficit, this research argues that even highly proficient faculty may occupy this ‘Third Space’ if the institutional community fails to provide mechanisms of mutual engagement (institutional support) and professional recognition (workplace inclusion).

Distinct from language proficiency, which is a skill, this study operationalizes linguistic belonging as a multi-dimensional affective construct comprising a sense of security in one’s voice, the ownership of English as a professional tool, and a perception of legitimacy within the academic community (Yuval-Davis, 2006). Conceptually, linguistic belonging is not a directly observable or stable attribute but an affective and relational condition that is revealed through everyday experiences of participation, recognition, and connection within social and institutional contexts. Following Yuval-Davis (2006), linguistic belonging is understood not merely as formal membership but as the lived sense of being accepted, heard, and legitimized within a community. In workplace settings, this sense of linguistic belonging often becomes visible through moments of strain or disruption, such as reduced confidence, self-censorship, or feeling overlooked, rather than through its seamless presence. Experiences of disconnection are treated as negative indicators of linguistic belonging and reflect constrained participation and weakened access to professional voice rather than individual linguistic deficiency.

This approach aligns with participation-based and workplace inclusion frameworks, which conceptualize inclusion and belonging as relational outcomes shaped by institutional and interpersonal conditions rather than solely by individual characteristics. By measuring reported linguistic disconnection, the study captures how language operates as a lived dimension of professional inclusion and exclusion in English-medium higher education. This approach intentionally utilizes negative indicators to mitigate social desirability bias, as NNES faculty may feel professional pressure to report high levels of belonging to signal institutional fit. By measuring reported linguistic disconnection, the study captures the lived reality of professional exclusion, treating the absence of such disconnection as a primary indicator of a secure sense of linguistic belonging.

To understand how this affective state of linguistic belonging is constructed, this research attempts to isolate specific factors that constrain or enable NNES academics’ sense of linguistic belonging in the UAE. First, it examines situational variables in the social domain—workplace inclusion and perceived institutional support—as the structural conditions that shape participation. Second, it analyzes individual variables in the personal domain, focusing on perceived language proficiency alongside academic acculturation factors such as rank, gender, and duration of residence in English-speaking environments. Furthermore, the study explores whether these patterns of belonging are uniform across the academic landscape or vary by disciplinary communication norms. By integrating these dimensions, the study explains how the demands of English-dominant academic work in a multilingual society shape not only performance but also the emotional and professional belonging of NNES academics. Importantly, linguistic belonging in this study is examined through its measurable indicator: self-reported experiences of linguistic (dis)connection in English-medium academic life. Rather than treating belonging as a stable trait, the study operationalizes it as faculty

members' self-reported experiences of feeling disconnected, less confident, or overlooked in English-mediated professional interactions. This conceptualization allows the study to link a language-and-identity concern to institutional and interpersonal conditions that can be addressed through policy and practice.

1.1. Ideological Foundations of Linguistic Belonging in EMI Contexts

Being competent in a language or not is shaped by broader ideological frameworks that link linguistic competence to professional belonging, institutional legitimacy, and access to academic and employment opportunities. Such framings present the success of learning a new language as a form of self-investment, with languages treated as both marketable skills and personal responsibilities, as conceptualized through linguistic entrepreneurship (De Costa *et al.*, 2020). These ideologies reinforce native-speaker hierarchies. Although such hierarchies have been widely critiqued through World Englishes and postcolonial perspectives (Canagarajah, 2006; Kachru, 1992; Matsuda, 2019), their effects continue to shape how English users are evaluated and how they perceive themselves within academic contexts. Related critiques—including the monolingual fallacy and native-speaker fallacy (Phillipson, 1992), the legitimate language myth (Watts, 2011), and the notion of native-speakerism (Holliday, 2006, 2008)—have drawn attention to the ideological roots of linguistic inequality in academic contexts, shaping language users' sense of linguistic belonging and legitimacy. However, this distinction is not purely linguistic. Rather, broader sociocultural and ideological forces shape linguistic belonging; these forces construct professional hierarchies that reinforce inequitable treatment within the profession (Selvi *et al.*, 2023). Taken together, this body of work suggests that linguistic belonging in EMI contexts is produced through ideologically structured judgments about what counts as legitimate language and who is authorized to utilize it. Importantly, such judgments do not remain abstract: they are experienced through everyday participation conditions that enable or constrain access to interaction, recognition, and professional voice in academic workplaces.

A key question, then, is how these ideological hierarchies become visible in everyday academic life. One mechanism is evaluative practice: the ways listeners interpret linguistic cues and convert them into judgments about competence, professionalism, and legitimacy. Research on accent-based perceptions illustrates how such cues can function as gatekeeping devices, shaping perceived proficiency and, consequently, individuals' sense of linguistic belonging. In workplace settings, these evaluative processes can also operate as exclusionary mechanisms by regulating who is heard as credible, who is treated as competent, and who feels able to participate fully. Ghosh *et al.* (2023) examine how linguistic and accent-based stereotypes shape listeners' perceptions. It has been found that non-native accents strongly influence evaluations of language proficiency, often misrepresenting actual performance. In addition, it is argued that increasing awareness of implicit linguistic biases can promote empathy, inclusion, and fairer evaluations, particularly in educational settings. Similarly, Abu Guba *et al.* (2023) contend that native-like accents are consistently rated higher, and even Arabic speakers demonstrate bias against their own regional varieties. The study highlights how accent prestige reinforces social and professional inequalities and calls for more inclusive linguistic environments to promote equity. Read through the lens of EMI, these findings help explain how legitimacy is not only claimed through competence but also conferred (or withheld) through socially recognizable markers that are treated as proxies for ability.

At the same time, legitimacy and linguistic belonging are not shaped only by how individuals are evaluated; they are also shaped by how language users navigate multilingual realities in practice, viewing language use as the strategic deployment of resources from a dynamic and integrated linguistic repertoire (Vogel & García, 2017; Wei, 2018). Building on this view, research on

translanguaging and identity highlights how belonging is performed and negotiated through everyday interaction, rather than anchored in fixed language categories or idealized norms (Creese & Blackledge, 2015). This perspective shifts attention away from evaluative regimes and toward how individuals actively use their multilingual resources to participate, collaborate, and sustain professional identities within EMI environments.

Nevertheless, multilingual and translanguaging practices do not fully remove the importance of language proficiency in shaping participation and linguistic belonging. In particular, language proficiency continues to function as a gatekeeper to access to interaction, social networks, and institutional support. For example, limited proficiency in the dominant language restricts access to social networks and institutional resources, while stronger language skills facilitate participation and trust, shaping individuals' linguistic belonging and social inclusion (Nawyn *et al.*, 2012). Comparable dynamics can be seen in educational settings where language proficiency continues to influence participation in classroom practices, even when translanguaging is encouraged (Moradkhani & Asakereh, 2018). In faculty workplaces, these dynamics suggest that proficiency can operate as a participation condition, shaping the extent to which individuals can access professional interaction, build trust, and secure recognition—thereby intensifying experiences of reduced or strained linguistic belonging.

Taken together, these studies illustrate that linguistic belonging is not just about language use or competence but is also shaped by translanguaging practices and ideological judgments about legitimacy, accent, and proficiency. Approaching linguistic belonging through the lens of constrained participation foregrounds how such judgments and participation conditions may be lived as disconnection—experienced in reduced voice, constrained participation, and limited access to institutional and collegial resources.

1.2. Navigating Linguistic Belonging: Non-Native Faculty in EMI Higher Education in the Gulf

The Gulf context provides a particularly salient site for examining how linguistic belonging is negotiated under EMI because language is deeply entangled with identity, policy, and social stratification. The emergence of a localized Gulf English raises important questions for language policy and the future role of Arabic. Arabic remains strongly linked to religion, tradition, and national identity, while English is becoming increasingly dominant in the Gulf (Siemund *et al.*, 2020). Within this sociolinguistic context, using English as the sole medium of instruction can be challenging for both teachers and students, particularly in complex subjects (Belhiah & Elhami, 2015). Limited English proficiency often shifts the focus from content learning to language management, producing tensions between promoting English and maintaining Arabic identity. This dynamic is evident in Dubai, where EMI both confers social and educational power and reinforces language inequalities, creating practical challenges for teachers in managing language use and student understanding (Hopkyns, 2020). This accords with the finding that native-speaker ideologies privilege British and American English in the Gulf, thereby marginalizing local Arab teachers and learners (Daoud & Kasztalska, 2022). In university settings, these tensions extend beyond classroom instruction to shape workplace participation, professional recognition, and linguistic belonging in institutional life.

Such language hierarchies and instructional challenges have broader implications for both teachers and students in EMI contexts, influencing professional identity, authority, and individuals' sense of linguistic belonging. Research shows that even though non-native teachers in EMI contexts bring valuable multilingual and pedagogical strengths, their linguistic belonging and professional identity are often challenged by native-speaker preferences and

institutional hierarchies. For example, even though non-native teachers demonstrate strengths such as bilingualism, strong grammatical knowledge, and insight into learners' needs, they face employability anxiety, job insecurity, and marginalization due to native-speaker preferences (Saba & Frangieh, 2021). This provides further evidence that native speaker teachers are often favored in hiring, although Omani and Arabic-speaking teachers hold more permanent positions (Al Muqarshi & Kaparou, 2023). In line with these challenges, expatriate faculty often face short-term contracts, heavy workloads, limited institutional support, and reduced opportunities for research, which can undermine long-term professional development and institutional commitment (Austin *et al.*, 2014). Similarly, non-native teachers in Saudi Arabia are not granted authority or professional recognition, even though they are valued for their pedagogical clarity (Alenazi, 2014). Together, these studies suggest that belonging is not only an interpersonal experience but also an institutional outcome shaped by hiring preferences, recognition regimes, and employment structures. Read as workplace participation conditions, these factors indicate that constrained linguistic belonging may be produced through restricted access to stable positions, limited institutional support, and constrained opportunities to develop professional voice and standing.

On the other hand, UAE university students tend to value non-native teachers for their pedagogical competence and supportive practices, even though native teachers are recognized for pronunciation, fluency, and linguistic authenticity (Awad *et al.*, 2024). Students' appreciation of non-native teachers highlights a pedagogical focus on instructional competence, emphasizing teaching skills over nativeness. This is further reflected in Gulf EMI contexts, where translanguaging and other multilingual strategies support effective classroom practices. For example, teachers in private EMI secondary schools in the UAE value and employ multilingual pedagogies, such as translanguaging and cross-linguistic comparison, yet their practices remain constrained by English-dominant institutional policies that privilege English and marginalize Arabic (Calafato, 2022). In the same vein, transnational teacher educators across the Arabian Gulf use learner-centered and reflective approaches to support national capacity building but often feel underutilized in institutional decision-making, with EMI and students' language proficiency remaining ongoing challenges (Gallagher, 2023). These findings point to a recurrent tension between pedagogical competence and institutional legitimacy, suggesting that inclusion in professional communities may depend not only on teaching practices but also on institutional climates that determine whose expertise is recognized and whose participation is enabled.

In light of these findings, effective support for teachers in EMI contexts requires attention to both classroom practices and institutional policies that recognize and build on teachers' multilingual strengths. Research suggests several strategies to address these professional and pedagogical challenges. These include adopting bilingual and flexible EMI practices (Belhiah & Elhami, 2015), mentoring and acknowledging non-native teachers' multilingual backgrounds (Hebbard, 2024), and recognizing teachers' multilingual resources alongside policy reforms (Calafato, 2022). These strategies align with calls for glocalised policies that support translanguaging practices and authentic linguistic identities (Hopkins & Elyas, 2022), as well as a 'knowledge code' approach that prioritizes linguistic proficiency and pedagogical expertise over nativeness (Daoud & Kasztalska, 2022). Namely, teacher effectiveness should be assessed based on training and pedagogical skills rather than linguistic background, thereby promoting more equitable and inclusive EMI practices (Alenazi, 2014). Collectively, these strategies create EMI environments that support teachers' professional growth, reinforce their linguistic belonging, and empower them to exercise pedagogical and linguistic agency within more equitable educational contexts. From the perspective of constrained linguistic belonging, such reforms

also imply that improving workplace inclusion and perceived institutional support may reduce experiences of disconnection by strengthening participation opportunities and institutional recognition for non-native English-speaking faculty.

Building on these insights, linguistic belonging can be approached through faculty members' reported experiences of participation in English-medium academic life, including experiences of disconnection in English-mediated interactions. In EMI workplaces, constrained linguistic belonging may be experienced not only through judgments about legitimate English (e.g., accent- and proficiency-based evaluations) but also through the institutional and interpersonal participation conditions that regulate access to collegial interaction, professional networks, and institutional resources. Alongside these conditions, individual linguistic resources and trajectories may shape how faculty experience participation, including perceived English proficiency and prior English-language socialization, which can influence confidence, interactional fluency, and professional self-positioning. In this study, prior English-language socialization is operationalized as years lived in English-speaking countries, acknowledging that English socialization can also occur through EMI schooling and transnational professional contexts. However, while Gulf-based EMI research has generated valuable insights into language policy, teacher identity, native-speaker hierarchies, and multilingual pedagogies, far less is known about linguistic belonging as a workplace experience among multilingual faculty in the UAE. Moreover, existing work rarely tests how institutional conditions of participation (such as workplace inclusion and perceived support) relate to reported disconnection in English-mediated professional life alongside individual linguistic resources and prior English-language socialization.

1.3. The Present Study

The present study contributes evidence on how language ideologies and institutional climates are lived as professional experience in the multilingual Gulf university. The study aims to systematically examine the factors associated with linguistic belonging among non-native English-speaking faculty in UAE EMI higher education. In doing so, this study seeks answers to the research questions given below:

1. To what extent is linguistic belonging in English-medium academic life (indexed through reported linguistic disconnection) associated with workplace inclusion, job satisfaction, and perceived institutional support among non-native English-speaking faculty in UAE higher education?
2. To what extent is linguistic belonging (indexed through reported linguistic disconnection) associated with self-rated English proficiency and prior English-language socialization (operationalized as years lived in English-speaking countries)?
3. Do these associations remain significant after accounting for gender, institutional type (public/private), academic rank, academic discipline and teaching experience (overall and in the UAE)?

2. Methods

2.1. Research Design

This study employed a cross-sectional survey design to examine linguistic belonging among non-native English-speaking (NNES) faculty at English-medium higher education institutions in the UAE. To maintain institutional anonymity as required by ethical protocols, specific university names are not disclosed; however, the sample includes representatives from all major types of higher education institutions in the UAE. The research investigated the relationships between linguistic connection and various demographic, linguistic, and institutional factors. Data were collected via Qualtrics using a survey instrument comprising scaled items and

multiple-choice questions. Faculty email addresses were obtained from publicly available university websites and departmental directories, and invitation emails explained the purpose of the study and provided a survey link. Eligible participants were full-time faculty members who self-identified as non-native English speakers. The survey was open from September 4 to November 6, participation was voluntary, and informed consent was obtained electronically.

2.2. Participants

The analytic sample of the study includes 245 valid responses. The participants represented nearly 50 nationalities, underscoring the highly international and multilingual character of UAE universities. The sample reflected a fairly even gender balance and representation from both public and private institutions, with 54.7% male and 45.3% female respondents, and an almost equal split between public (49.4%) and private (50.6%) sectors. In terms of professional standing, the cohort was notably experienced; nearly half (49.4%) held senior ranks as Professor or Associate Professor, with Assistant Professors comprising the largest single group at 33.9%. While the participants represented a broad disciplinary spectrum, the highest concentrations were observed in Arts & Humanities (21.6%), Engineering & Technology (14.7%), and Social Sciences (13.9%), reflecting a diverse cross-section of the UAE's academic workforce.

Table 1.
Demographic Characteristics of Participants

Labels	Descriptors	f	%
Gender	Male	134	54.7
	Female	111	45.3
Academic discipline	Arts & Humanities	53	21.6
	Computer Science & Artificial Intelligence	10	4.1
	Economics & Business	32	13.1
	Education	23	9.4
	Engineering & Technology	36	14.7
	Life Sciences & Biology	12	4.9
	Medicine & Health Sciences	26	10.6
	Physical Sciences	19	7.8
	Social Sciences	34	13.9
	Institution Type	Public	121
Private		124	50.6
Professor		53	21.6
Current Academic Rank	Associate Professor	68	27.8
	Assistant Professor	83	33.9
	Lecturer/Instructor	41	16.7

2.3. Measures

2.3.1. Dependent variable: Linguistic belonging

Linguistic belonging is operationalized as self-reported linguistic disconnection within English-mediated academic and professional interactions. The scale captures nuanced experiences of alienation, such as feeling disconnected, less confident, or overlooked in everyday collegial communication. To minimize social desirability bias—where participants might over-report “belonging” to appear more integrated—the scale utilized seven negatively worded items. These items were coded such that higher scores indicate greater linguistic disconnection (i.e., weaker linguistic belonging). The items included:

1. I feel disconnected from the English-speaking community at my institution.
2. I feel less of a sense of belonging when I interact with native English speakers.

3. My language background makes me feel like an outsider in academic settings.
4. I feel excluded from informal professional conversations because of language references.
5. I feel less confident participating in collaborative projects because of language-related concerns.
6. I feel that my ideas are overlooked or dismissed because of how I speak English.
7. Language barriers reduce my sense of professional belonging within my institution.

The seven items were averaged to create the Linguistic Belonging Index, which demonstrated excellent internal consistency (Cronbach's alpha = .888). An exploratory factor analysis (EFA) further confirmed a single-factor structure, with all items loading strongly on one factor. This supports the index's unidimensionality and confirms that the items collectively tap into a singular construct of linguistic belonging in the EMI workplace.

2.3.2. Independent variables

The independent variables of the study are English proficiency, institutional support, workplace inclusion, job satisfaction, experience, and demographic variables. With reference to English proficiency, participants provided a self-assessment of their overall English proficiency on a scale from 1 to 10, encompassing the four core domains of reading, writing, speaking, and listening. This rating is participant's own evaluation of their perceived language competence and did not require participants to justify their self-ratings. Institutional Support was measured using a single-item indicator that asked faculty to rate the extent to which they feel supported by their institution in fulfilling their professional responsibilities. Responses were recorded on a scale from 1 to 10. Workplace inclusion was measured using a 7-item scale assessing respect, recognition, and institutional involvement. Participants responded to the following statements using a 5-point Likert scale (1. Strongly Disagree to 5. Strongly Agree):

1. I feel that I am a valued member of my academic department.
2. I feel included in important professional discussions and decision-making processes.
3. My professional contributions are recognized and appreciated by colleagues.
4. I feel that my background and identity are respected at my institution.
5. I believe I have equal opportunities for leadership and advancement compared to my colleagues.
6. I feel that my opinions are respected in meetings and discussions.
7. I feel that I must work harder than others to be accepted as an equal professional.

The items were averaged to create the Workplace Inclusion Index, with the negatively worded item (Item 7) reverse-coded to ensure higher scores consistently indicated stronger levels of inclusion. The index showed strong reliability (Cronbach's alpha .824). Higher scores indicate stronger inclusion. Job satisfaction was measured using a single-item global indicator asking respondents to rate their overall satisfaction with their experience as a faculty member at their current institution on a scale from 0 to 10. Higher scores indicate greater job satisfaction. As for their experiences, the participants indicated their teaching experience and years spent in an English-speaking country. Participants reported their Years Spent in English-Speaking Countries, using a categorical scale (ranging from none to more than ten years). Teaching Experience was captured through two variables: total years of teaching and years of teaching specifically within the UAE. Finally, demographic and professional Information was collected, including gender, institution type, and academic rank.

2.4. Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression to examine the predictors of linguistic belonging among NNEs faculty. OLS was determined to be the most

appropriate method because the dependent variable—the Linguistic Belonging Index—is a continuous measure constructed from multiple Likert-type items, yielding a wide observed range and an approximately normal distribution. Prior to model estimation, the data were screened for violations of linear regression assumptions. Linearity and homoscedasticity were assessed via residual plots, and normality of residuals was confirmed. To ensure coefficients stability, multicollinearity was evaluated using Variance Inflation Factors (VIF); all VIF values were well below the standard threshold of 10 (and typically below 2.5), indicating no significant collinearity among independent variables such as English proficiency and years of experience. Furthermore, supplementary analyses using alternative model specifications—including robust standard errors—produced substantively similar results, confirming the reliability and parsimony of the OLS approach. Results are reported with unstandardized coefficients (β), standard errors, and varying levels of confidence intervals ($*p < .05$, $**p < .01$, $***p < .001$) for significant differences.

3. Results

3.1. Descriptive Statistics

The sample reflects a highly experienced faculty body, with nearly half (46.5%) of respondents reporting more than 15 years of total teaching experience. However, tenure in the UAE varied significantly; while a majority had taught in the country for at least 2 years, only 17.6% had reached the 15-year mark locally, suggesting a workforce that transitioned to the UAE after established careers elsewhere. Exposure to English-speaking countries was similarly diverse: while 44.1% of the sample had lived in such environments for six years or more, a substantial minority (29.0%) reported no residency in English-speaking nations.

Table 2.

Descriptive Statistics of Variables

Labels	Variables	f	%	
Years of total teaching experience	1 year or less	2	0.8	
	2 to 5 years	32	13.1	
	6 to 10 years	44	18.0	
	11 to 15 years	53	21.6	
	More than 15 years	114	46.5	
Years of teaching experience in the UAE	1 year or less	18	7.3	
	2 to 5 years	78	31.8	
	6 to 10 years	50	20.4	
	11 to 15 years	56	22.9	
	More than 15 years	43	17.6	
Years in English-speaking countries	None	71	29.0	
	Less than 1 year	12	4.9	
	1 – 2 years	19	7.8	
	3 – 5 years	35	14.3	
	6 – 10 years	62	25.3	
	More than 10 years	46	18.8	
	Mean	St.Dev.	Min	Max
Workplace inclusion index	28.55	4.44	11	35
Linguistic belonging index	10.91	4.41	7	28
Overall English proficiency	8.99	1.05	4	10
Institutional support	8.23	1.74	0	10
Job Satisfaction	8.26	1.53	1	10

Despite these varying backgrounds, participants reported high levels of Overall English Proficiency (M=8.99, SD=1.05) and generally positive perceptions of their professional environment, with strong ratings for both Institutional Support (M=8.23, SD=1.74) and Job Satisfaction (M=8.26, SD=1.53). These sentiments are mirrored in the Workplace Inclusion Index, which yielded a mean of 28.55 (out of 35). Notably, the Linguistic Belonging Index, where higher scores represent greater linguistic disconnection, resulted in a low mean of 10.91 (out of 28), suggesting that, on average, the faculty experience relatively low levels of linguistic disconnection, indicating a robust sense of belonging within their respective academic communities.

3.2. Regression Analysis

To identify the factors most strongly associated with linguistic belonging, an ordinary least squares (OLS) regression was estimated using the Linguistic Belonging Index as the dependent variable. As previously noted, lower scores on this index indicate stronger linguistic belonging, while higher scores reflect greater linguistic disconnection. The model explained approximately 43% of the variance (Adjusted R-squared = .426), suggesting a moderate to strong overall fit.

Table 3.

OLS Regression Model Examining Associations with Linguistic Belonging

Variables	β	St. Err.	Sig.
Workplace inclusion index	-.477	.063	***
Overall English proficiency	-1.708	.229	***
Institutional support	-.071	.171	
Job satisfaction	.278	.198	
Years in English-speaking countries	-.026	.129	
Years of total teaching experience	-.203	.257	
Years of teaching experience in the UAE	-.067	.227	
Male	-.300	.494	
Public university	-.726	.475	
Associate professor	.207	.671	
Assistant professor	-.439	.733	
Lecturer/Instructor	.112	.850	
Computer science and artificial intelligence	-2.042	1.215	
Economics and business	-1.925	.796	*
Education	-.123	.889	
Engineering and technology	-.676	.790	
Life sciences and biology	-2.797	1.146	*
Medicine and health sciences	-1.948	.844	*
Physical sciences	-1.996	.957	*
Social sciences	-1.648	.799	*
(Constant)	41.135	2.680	***
Adjusted R-squared	0.426		
N	245		

Notes: Females, private university, professor, and Arts and Humanities are reference categories. β denotes the unstandardized coefficients. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$ *** $p < .001$.

3.2.1. Significant variables

Two variables showed clear and highly significant associations with linguistic belonging: workplace inclusion and overall English proficiency. Workplace inclusion demonstrated a strong negative association with linguistic belonging ($\beta = -.477$, $p < .001$). Because lower

scores on the Linguistic Belonging Index indicate stronger belonging, the negative coefficient suggests that faculty who feel more included, valued, and respected within their institution are also more likely to experience linguistic connection and confidence in everyday professional interaction. This pattern underscores how social and institutional climates shape not only formal inclusion; but also the lived and experienced language in daily academic practice. In short, when faculty feel included in broader workplace structures, they also tend to experience stronger linguistic belonging.

Overall English proficiency was also a powerful predictor of linguistic belonging ($\beta = -1.708$, $p < .001$). Faculty who rated their English proficiency more highly reported significantly stronger feelings of linguistic ease and inclusion. This result aligns with expectations, as greater proficiency can reduce hesitation, anxiety, or feelings of exclusion in English-medium environments. The strength of the coefficient indicates that proficiency remains an important personal resource shaping how faculty navigate informal and professional communication.

Several academic disciplines showed significant associations with linguistic belonging. Compared to the reference group (Arts and Humanities), faculty in several fields reported stronger linguistic belonging, indicated by negative coefficients. Statistically significant effects were observed in: Economics and Business ($\beta = -1.925$, $p < .05$), Life Sciences and Biology ($\beta = -2.797$, $p < .05$), Medicine and Health Sciences ($\beta = -1.948$, $p < .05$), Physical Sciences ($\beta = -1.996$, $p < .05$), and Social Sciences ($\beta = -1.648$, $p < .05$). Faculty in these disciplines reported notably lower Linguistic Belonging Index scores, suggesting stronger linguistic belonging compared to the reference category. This may reflect disciplinary communication norms, linguistic cultures within departments, or different expectations for informal and collaborative interactions. For example, some disciplines may rely more on structured or technical communication, while others may involve more embedded networks or shared linguistic practices that facilitate belonging. Computer Science and Engineering also showed negative coefficients, though these results did not reach significance. Education showed no statistically significant results

3.2.2. *Non-significant variables*

Institutional support and job satisfaction did not show statistically significant relationships with linguistic belonging. Although both variables had coefficients in the expected directions, with institutional support slightly reducing linguistic disconnection (as greater support is expected to mitigate feelings of disconnection) and job satisfaction slightly increasing it (as higher satisfaction may coexist with persistent linguistic challenges), neither effect reached statistical significance. This suggests that while support and satisfaction contribute to broader workplace experiences, they do not, on their own, shape how linguistically connected faculty feel when other factors are considered.

Neither gender nor institutional type (public or private) was associated with differences in linguistic belonging. Similarly, academic rank showed no significant effects, indicating that professors, associate professors, assistant professors, and lecturers do not differ meaningfully in how linguistically connected they feel.

Years of total teaching experience and years of teaching experience within the UAE were also unrelated to linguistic belonging. This indicates that linguistic connection in the workplace is not simply a function of professional seniority or adaptation to the local academic environment. Likewise, time spent living in English-speaking countries before moving to the UAE did not predict feelings of linguistic belonging. These non-significant findings suggest that past exposure to English-speaking contexts may matter less than present-day institutional and interpersonal dynamics.

4. Discussion

Taken together, the regression results suggest that linguistic belonging among non-native English-speaking faculty in UAE higher education is shaped primarily by institutional climate and linguistic capability, rather than by demographic or career characteristics. Faculty who feels included within their departments and institutions, and those with stronger self-rated English proficiency, tend to feel more linguistically confident and connected. In contrast, factors such as gender, rank, institutional type, teaching experience, or time spent in English-speaking countries do not play significant roles.

The significant disciplinary differences also highlight that linguistic belonging is not uniform across the academic landscape. Some fields may foster more linguistically inclusive environments or rely on communication styles that help non-native English-speaking faculty feel more at ease. These findings underscore the importance of institutional practices and departmental cultures in shaping how faculty experience language in their daily professional lives.

The findings of this study reveal that even in EMI settings where the external pressure to conform to native-speaker standards may theoretically be lower than in Anglophone contexts, the internal experience of linguistic belonging remains fragile. Our results show that overall English proficiency is a powerful predictor of belonging, suggesting that when faculty perceive their own linguistic resources as insufficient, a process of linguistic disconnection occurs. This disconnection is not merely a technical issue; it is a profound internal shift where the individual feels their professional voice is weakened, leading to a sense of being “outsiders within.” Despite the multicultural nature of the UAE’s academic landscape, NNES faculty still navigate a significant tension between their self-perceived proficiency and their professional identity, resulting in a lived experience of linguistic disconnection that mirrors the challenges found in native-dominant environments.

Although native-speaker ideologies are not directly addressed in this study, proficiency in English is a core component of linguistic belonging. This is not surprising, as the study explored linguistic belonging in EMI higher educational institutions. Nevertheless, it is worth noting that within EMI contexts, even in contexts where English proficiency is generally high, sociolinguistic factors such as accent awareness and fear of negative judgment may subtly constrain participation and confidence in interaction. This aligns with the work of Abu Guba *et al.* (2023), who examined how accents can generate biases among faculty, as well as the work on how accent-related stereotypes influence our perceptions of each other (Ghosh *et al.*, 2023). Proficiency promotes linguistic belonging, whereas perceived speech and communication incongruities have the opposite effect. Taken together, these findings suggest that linguistic belonging is shaped not only by functional language competence but also by how language use is socially evaluated in professional settings. This reinforces the importance of examining linguistic belonging as an affective and relational experience within the academic Community of Practice, rather than merely a function of proficiency alone.

While not explicitly measured in this study, the broader Gulf EMI context suggests that Arabic proficiency can function as a resource for inclusion rather than as a barrier. Studies indicate that multilingual faculty who can engage with students in Arabic may strengthen classroom interaction and institutional integration (Al Muqarshi & Kaparou, 2023). This points to a broader tension between the expansion of English as the dominant academic medium and the continued symbolic and practical significance of Arabic in everyday institutional life. At the same time, it may reflect positive language management, in which faculty recognize the value of both English for academic communication and Arabic for student engagement and collegial

interaction. Such dynamics are consistent with research on Emirati students' code-switching practices between Arabic and English (Van den Hoven & Carroll, 2020) and with the multilingual composition of faculty in UAE universities, where Arabic-speaking staff constitutes a substantial proportion of the work force. In this context, linguistic belonging is negotiated within a multilingual ecology in which English and Arabic carry different but complementary functions.

In this sense, linguistic belonging in the UAE appears to be negotiated within a multilingual environment in which English and Arabic serve different symbolic and practical functions. Rather than replacing Arabic, English operates alongside it, shaping professional interaction in ways that may benefit multilingual faculty while simultaneously reproducing new boundaries of inclusion and exclusion. These findings have broader implications for understanding the academic profession in internationalized higher education systems. Linguistic belonging emerges as a condition shaping how faculty develop professional voice, participate in collegial interaction, and experience recognition within departmental life. In this sense, language does not simply function as a medium of communication but as a resource that structures access to mutual engagement, including collaboration, informal exchange, and the negotiation of expertise as a legitimate member of the professional community.

Given that our empirical results also identified workplace inclusion as a primary predictor of linguistic belonging, institutions should prioritize creating spaces for shared practice and mutual recognition while helping faculty further develop their English language proficiency. This could take the form of increased faculty research collaboration or seminar series which provide all interested faculty members with a chance to share their research with colleagues at the departmental, college, or institutional levels. Another initiative that could enhance faculty members' proficiency is the establishment of international, cross-institutional networks that enable faculty to interact with academics at EMI universities worldwide.

Importantly, these initiatives may also normalize diverse linguistic practices and reduce anxiety associated with informal academic interaction. By creating structured yet inclusive spaces for participation, institutions can indirectly strengthen linguistic confidence and professional voice among non-native English-speaking faculty. This study demonstrated that institutional support and job satisfaction—factors often prioritized by university administrations—do not significantly impact linguistic belonging as much as the quality of social and professional inclusion. This finding can be interpreted as a shift in focus: when faculty perceive themselves as esteemed and legitimate members of their academic community, formal institutional support aimed at language remediation becomes less critical. This finding is transformative: it suggests that while a faculty member may struggle with their own sense of linguistic “adequacy,” a supportive and inclusive Community of Practice can bridge that gap. When a faculty member is treated as an esteemed and legitimate colleague whose expertise is recognized beyond their linguistic performance, the psychological weight of disconnection diminishes. In other words, workplace inclusion functions as a corrective social force that re-establishes the ties between the individual and the community, proving that a secure sense of belonging is a relational outcome rather than a purely individual linguistic achievement.

EMI contexts, both in the UAE and globally, must embrace the richness that multilingualism brings to the workplace and foster collaborative practices where all speakers, regardless of their native or non-native status, receive equitable treatment and recognition. Failure to maintain this balance—whether intentional or unintentional—may heighten long-term tensions and lead to linguistic discrimination, negatively impacting the collective academic environment. Ultimately, linguistic belonging must be conceptualized as an integral part of

identity formation; faculty should feel they are valued members of the professional community based on their expertise and engagement, rather than being judged solely on their linguistic functionality.

5. Limitations and Future Research

Several limitations should be considered when interpreting the findings of this study. The analysis is based on a cross-sectional survey, which captures linguistic belonging at a single point in time. Because linguistic belonging is likely to evolve as faculty gain experience within institutions, departments, or national contexts, longitudinal research would be useful for understanding how these experiences change over the course of academic careers in EMI environments.

Linguistic belonging in this study is measured through self-reported experiences of linguistic disconnection. While this approach is theoretically grounded and well-suited to capturing affective and relational dimensions of language use, it may also reflect individual response styles or momentary perceptions. Future research could build on this work by combining survey data with interviews, ethnographic observation, or interactional analysis to examine how linguistic belonging is enacted and negotiated in everyday academic practices.

English proficiency and institutional conditions were also measured using self-assessment rather than externally validated indicators. Although self-rated proficiency is widely used in sociolinguistic and workplace research and reflects lived linguistic confidence, future studies could strengthen measurement by triangulating with alternative indicators, such as peer assessments, task-based measures, or patterns of language use across professional contexts.

In addition, while the sample includes faculty from a wide range of disciplines, institutions, and national backgrounds, the study is situated within the specific sociolinguistic and institutional context of the United Arab Emirates. The UAE represents a highly internationalized and multilingual higher education environment, and the findings may not fully generalize to English-medium instruction contexts elsewhere. Comparative research across regions and institutional settings would help clarify which aspects of linguistic belonging are context-specific and which reflect broader features of English-dominant academic work.

Finally, the disciplinary differences observed in this study should be understood as exploratory. Although the associations reported here are exploratory, the researchers could not confirm, at the 5% significance level, that being a faculty in Education, Engineering and Technology, or Computer Science and Artificial Intelligence correlated with higher levels of linguistic belonging. The observed disciplinary differences should be interpreted as patterns that warrant further investigation rather than definitive explanations, particularly given differences in disciplinary size, organization, and everyday modes of professional interaction. Future research could examine disciplinary cultures more closely by focusing on communication norms, collaboration practices, mentoring structures, and evaluation criteria within departments. Qualitative and mixed-methods approaches would be particularly valuable for unpacking how disciplinary contexts shape participation, recognition, and linguistic belonging in more nuanced ways. Taken together, these considerations point to several promising directions for future research. Expanding the study of linguistic belonging across time, contexts, and methodological approaches would deepen understanding of how language shapes professional inclusion and academic life in multilingual higher education systems.

6. Conclusion

This study investigated linguistic belonging among non-native English-speaking faculty at EMI higher education institutions in the United Arab Emirates. Two variables were found to be

closely associated with linguistic belonging: workplace inclusion and English proficiency. Feelings of inclusion in broader workplace structures seem to promote a sense of linguistic belonging among our sample. This is a novel finding that needs to be validated through future research on EMI higher education institutions. By highlighting the role of workplace inclusion, this study shifts attention away from individual linguistic deficits and toward institutional and relational conditions that shape everyday academic participation.

Proficiency in English at EMI higher education institutions serves as a personal resource that shapes how faculty navigate formal and informal communication at work. Since EMI higher education institutions, by definition, rely on English as a language of instruction and regular communication within the institution, higher proficiency in English unsurprisingly has a positive effect on linguistic belonging. This study confirmed the extent to which overall English proficiency positively impacts linguistic belonging. This finding underscores the continued relevance of language proficiency even in highly international and multilingual academic environments, while also suggesting that proficiency alone does not guarantee a sense of belonging.

A surprising finding in this study was that neither institutional support nor job satisfaction affected linguistic belonging. This may indicate that while institutional support can improve areas such as research output, workload, and so on, it plays a minimal role in promoting linguistic belonging. It may also indicate that job satisfaction and linguistic belonging have very little influence on one another (namely, that one is satisfied with their employment while feeling little to no linguistic belonging, and vice versa). This finding warrants further exploration, as it challenges the assumption that job satisfaction is a key determinant of most outcomes and attitudes at work. Future research may benefit from examining whether linguistic belonging operates as a distinct dimension of academic life, shaped by interactional experiences rather than general employment conditions.

This study also noted disciplinary differences in linguistic belonging. Faculty in certain disciplines (e.g., Social sciences, Economics and Business, Medicine and Health sciences) were more likely to feel higher levels of linguistic belonging than faculty in other disciplines (e.g., Education, Engineering and Technology). Future research is needed to understand the underlying factors and to determine whether these disciplinary differences apply across time and geographic regions. The disciplinary patterns identified in this study should be read as indicative rather than explanatory and highlight the need for future research to examine how disciplinary cultures and institutional practices shape linguistic belonging over time and across contexts. Finally, this paper demonstrates the viability of treating linguistic belonging as a distinct analytical construct. Future research on faculty working in higher education institutions characterized by multiculturalism or multilingualism could benefit from including linguistic belonging in its scope. Using linguistic belonging as a discrete analytical construct may help researchers better understand the challenges faculty face across a wide range of institutions worldwide.

What, then, do the findings of this study suggest for the future of EMI institutions? Beyond the statistical associations, our results reveal a critical psychological reality: even in settings where the external pressure to conform to native-speaker standards is theoretically lower, the internal experience of linguistic belonging remains fragile. This study suggests that language proficiency is not a sufficient guarantee of belonging if the social conditions of inclusion are absent; conversely, a high degree of workplace inclusion can mitigate the psychological burden of perceived linguistic gaps. For institutions, this indicates a fundamental shift in responsibility:

fostering a sense of belonging among faculty is not merely a matter of technical language remediation, but of structural and relational recognition.

To enhance linguistic belonging, institutions—particularly those in EMI settings—should move beyond seeing English as a monolithic standard and instead focus on cultivating a Community of Practice that values diverse professional voices. Rather than investing solely in linguistic training, universities should prioritize creating inclusive spaces where every member's expertise is recognized and where professional legitimacy is decoupled from native-speakerist norms. Ultimately, when faculty are treated as esteemed and legitimate colleagues, the 'linguistic disconnection' that often plagues non-native speakers is replaced by a secure professional identity, ensuring a more cohesive and productive academic environment.

Ethical Statement

Ethical permission for this study was obtained from the Institutional Review Board of the American University of Sharjah (Protocol No. 25-101).

Informed Consent

A written informed consent form was obtained from each participant.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability

The data presented in this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request. For privacy reasons, the data from this study are not publicly available.

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